

Effectiveness Of Introducing Artificial Intelligence And Expert Systems In The Curricula And Teaching Methods Of Education Colleges

Hani Yousef Jarrah, Suad Alwaely

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 20, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: June 21, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Artificial Intelligence, Expert Systems, Teaching Methods.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12208078</p>	<p><i>This research examined educators' perceptions of the effectiveness of introducing artificial intelligence (A.I.) and expert systems into the curricula and teaching methods of higher educational institutions in the United Arab Emirates. Ninety-three faculty members in various departments of UAE colleges of education completed a questionnaire assessing the impacts of Artificial Intelligence on students' creativity, problem-solving skills, data were analyzed to identify differences based on gender, educational qualification, and experience.</i></p> <p><i>The results of t-tests and ANOVA analysis revealed that participants had overall positive attitudes toward introducing A.I. and expert systems into the curricula and teaching methods. Although no differences were found based on gender or experience, statistically significant differences were associated with academic qualifications, whereby participants with master's degrees gave higher ratings than those with doctorates. Based on the findings, introducing A.I. and expert systems into higher education curricula and teaching methods is recommended.</i></p>

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (A.I.) is among the most rapidly developing multimedia educational technologies (Al-Shahri, 2016). The rate of use of Artificial intelligence and expert systems is proportional to the increasing number of courseware inventions among educational colleges (Gebhardt, 2018). Over the past 2–3 decades, the development of tools for multimedia technology-enhanced student learning has accelerated quickly to enhance the interactive capabilities of students as well as educators. Multimedia tools have immensely benefitted educational institutions across fields, fostering learners' problem-solving abilities and communication and thereby augmenting their creativity, imagination, and cognition, as well as enhancing teachers' planning by providing insights into student aptitudes and learning processes.

Natural language processing (NLP) abilities and social intelligence embedded in A.I. give machines the ability to read and understand human languages as well as to adapt to different learning styles, aptitudes, and rates. Expert systems, which are a type of A.I. comprising software programs, have human influence approaches to problem-solving (Zayed, & Rahman, 2017).

The application of expert systems offers many advantages that support the educational process (Movafegh, Ghadirli & Rastgarpour, 2012). The chief benefit of an expert system is its ability to act as a "smart" teacher; thus, enabling independent learning outside of the classroom. The expert system also interacts with the learner by asking a set of questions and providing its conclusions in the form of diagnoses or suggested treatments. A similar process to the humanistic approach is to solve complex problems. A.I. and expert systems operate at a constant scientific and consultative level that is stable (Clement, 1992). This technology provides students with enjoyment that differs from traditional methods and introduces students' happiness and creativity in education, helping them imagine all that is new.

The main objective of this study was to assess different perceptions on the effectiveness of A.I. expert system implementation on the curricula and teaching method in education colleges, a case of Colleges of Education in the United Arab Emirates.

Accurately, this research measured perceptions of faculty members at Colleges of Education in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) regarding the effectiveness of introducing A.I. and expert systems in the curricula and teaching methods on the students' creativity and the problem-solving ability.

The research questions relevant for this study include 1) how the Artificial Intelligence expert systems implementation has influenced the curricula and teaching methods of education colleges? 2) How does the

implementation of the Artificial Intelligence systems in education colleges affect the creativity and the student's ability to solve problems?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The meaning of A.I. and how it works in educational colleges

A.I. refers to the aptitude exhibited by machines or software (Claudé and Combe 2018), and the field of A.I. researches how to create computers and computer programs capable of intelligent behavior. Baker and Smith (2019) defined A.I. rather broadly as "computers which perform cognitive tasks, usually associated with human minds, particularly learning and problem-solving" (p. 10). As they explained, A.I. describes a range of technologies and methods, including machine learning, natural language processing, data mining, neural networks, and algorithms. Artificial intelligence systems execute tasks that usually need human intelligence, such as visual insight, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages (Jewandah 2018).

Accordingly, the A.I. field draws upon multiple disciplines, including computer science, information engineering, mathematics, linguistics, psychology, and philosophy. Based on the simulation of the human mind, A.I. technology has belonged to the science of algorithms and intelligent techniques based on replicating and understanding the archetype of the human psyche. The human brain sends signals to the body, which in turn controls all social processes and activities that occur daily, such as feeling, sensing, thinking, and movement. A.I. was introduced to emulate these processes and has had some success.

A.I. and expert systems have published several studies on the development across diverse areas such as medicine, chemistry, physics, engineering, education and training, manufacturing, and management (Tan et al. 2016). Claudé and Combe (2018) highlighted the effectiveness of A.I. as a tool for managing complex situations. A.I. and its branches of expert systems can address complex problems in record time, which accelerates the process of accumulating new knowledge by presenting the information in a manner tailored to learner's needs, thereby enhancing their reasoning skills and ability to conclude. Additionally, the A.I. make the content easily memorizable by the students and make the work more comfortable for the teachers who prefer using them.

Jewandah (2018) emphasized that improvement and development in the A.I. industry would increase productivity for organizations at a lower cost.

2.2. The role of A.I. in the achievement of educational goals

The implementation of multimedia technology in higher education has been recognized as critical to maintain educational quality and achieve global competitiveness (Duncan 2010; Popenici and Kerr 2017; Warschauer 2004). Accordingly, countries with highly developed higher education systems are increasingly incorporating multimedia and mobile technologies as intrinsic elements of new "connected learning" networked economies. However, educators have only recently begun to explore the potential pedagogical opportunities that A.I. applications afford for supporting learners throughout their education (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Many teachers are yet to understand the benefits of I.A. in schools. They have a limited understanding of its pedagogical uses and have many questions regarding how to integrate A.I. as a supportive resource. (Hinojo-Lucena et al. 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). A.I. can impede students' imagination and learning self-efficiency if not applied to the university curriculum in a creative and balanced manner. As a result, the students may complete courses and graduate without enhancing their level of performance, development, and innovation.

Zayed and Rahman (2017) highlighted how expert systems and their dimensions, such as hardware, software, and knowledge engineering, have a statistically significant impact on the quality of decision-making. This finding was confirmed by Raqiq (2015), who established that A.I. applications could provide substantial assistance to employees in the completion of their tasks because of their superior ability to perform tasks perceived as painful.

Al-Bishtawi and Al-Buqami (2015) underscored the importance of expert systems in banks in facilitating electronic audit procedures such as swiftness in task execution and obtaining necessary data and information. A.I. enhanced the efficiency and quality of the audit by saving effort, time, and costs allocated to the implementation of the audit procedures and plan.

2.3. Expert systems as educational tools

Expert systems—the most notable applications of A.I.—transfer the logical processes of the human mind and present these consistent processes through a machine. Khanna et al. (2010) defined expert systems as a computer application that resolves complicated issues that need vast human experience; it simulates rational thinking using precise knowledge and interfaces. Additionally, these systems employ human expertise to solve the problems that usually require human intelligence. Expert systems have an immense capacity to carry out tasks, have access to rare knowledge and expertise, and seek to preserve it and facilitate their use in specific areas by applying multiple

perspectives to identify appropriate solutions to complex problems (Ishak, Hussain, Ku-Mahamud, & Md Norwawi, 2010). Expert systems can provide solutions, answer questions, or provide advice at similar to or higher levels than that provided by human experts in the same field (Lucas & van der Gaag, 1991). In this way, users can exploit their insights and experiences using the analytical and data retrieval powers of the system (Keen, 1980).

The teaching processes employed by expert systems include dynamic and rational training, and they play a critical role in enhancing teaching so that both teachers and students become interested and engaged in the learning process. These processes can then be used in educational curricula to promote and improve students' performance by fostering creative skills such as thinking, imagination, and cognition.

Madhu, Stella, and Eze (2017) emphasized the promotion of an expert system in the Nigerian educational system, finding that the tool provided great assistance for repeated study and understanding. Organizations can lose more of their useful problem-solving and analytical capabilities if A.I. technology and expert systems get neglected. Hassan, 2010). Using artificial intelligence applications in university libraries: designing an expert reference system for the University of Khartoum Library. University of Khartoum, Sudan. (Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis)] identified the uses and efficacy of A.I. in libraries, finding that librarians' insufficient knowledge of artificial intelligence affected their understanding of any type of practical application in libraries and how to extract knowledge and use it in information bases in expert systems in libraries.

2.4. Expert systems as educational tools

The success or failure of educational technology use is highly dependent on teachers' attitudes toward technology. Teachers' technology self-efficacy is a critical factor in attitudes toward educational technology and the propensity to utilize it. Some studies have indicated that men tend to have higher computer self-efficacy than women (Koch et al., 2008; Ong and Lai, 2006; Sieverding and Koch, 2009), which can affect their attitudes towards its usefulness for education. Wong et al. 's study (2005) found that the effect of computer teaching efficacy on perceived value and attitude toward computer use was significant for women student teachers but not for their male counterparts.

Several studies have applied technology acceptance models (TAM) to assess teachers' perceptions of the usefulness, ease of use, and attitudes toward technology use and education in the classroom (Wong et al. 2012). Wong et al. 's (2012) study of a sample of Malaysian teachers found that their TAM model accounted for 36.8% of the variance in intention to use computers among student teachers, and significant differences were identified based on computer teaching efficacy and gender.

Other researchers have used different measures to evaluate teachers' attitudes toward technology. Some studies have reported more positive attitudes towards technology among males than females (Chou et al. 2011; Durndell and Haag 2002; Durndell et al. 2000; Kay, 2009; Kesici et al. 2009; Ong and Lai, 2006). Cai et al. 's (2015) meta-analysis of gendered attitudes toward technology use revealed that males tend to hold more favorable attitudes toward technology use than females. However, some studies have found the opposite (Chen and Tsai, 2007; Johnson, 2011; Price, 2006), and others indicate no significant differences (Imhoff et al. 2007; Teo et al. 2015, 2016). For example, Teo et al. (2015, 2016) examined pre-service teachers' perceptions regarding the use of educational technology in Southeast Asia and Serbia, respectively, and found no significant differences based on gender.

3. METHOD AND PROCEDURES

3.1. Population and Sample

This study used the survey method to collect quantitative data using questionnaires. Random sampling identified 93 faculty members from the college of education in 5 UAE Universities. To gather the whole sample from the population of the five UAE universities using the simple sampling technique, 15-17 faculty members were selected from each university. Data collection occurs during the second semester of the academic year 2018/2019. Table 1 presents a summary of the participants according to gender, educational qualification, and years of experience.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Gender.</i>	Male	55	59.1
	Female	38	40.9
	Total	93	100.0
<i>Educational Qualification</i>	M.AMA.	40	43.0
	Ph.D.	53	57.0
	Total	93	100.0

<i>Experience</i>	<5 years	10	10.8
	5–10 years	44	47.3
	>10 years	39	41.9
	Total	1093	10.8100

Table 1: Distribution of the study sample

3.2. Instrument

Data collection was collected using a two-part tool. The first part collected primary socio-demographic data (gender, educational qualification, experience). The second part comprised 25 questions measuring faculty's perceptions of the effectiveness of the introduction of A.I. and expert systems in the curricula and teaching methods of university education colleges. A five-point Likert scale scored the responses. The case ranged from 5 = completely agree to 1 = disagree.

The questionnaire was presented to a group of arbitrators to ensure its reliability. After an initial review, some paragraphs got deleted, new sections added, and others modified. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient used to verify the scale's stability and internal consistency calculated resulted in a high value of 0.932.

3.3. Statistical processing

Frequencies and percentages of personal information, arithmetic averages, and standard deviations of questionnaires used for developing questionnaire paragraphs. An independent-sample t-test applied to variables with two categories and analysis of variance (ANOVA) used to variables with more than two groups.

4. RESULTS

<i>No.</i>	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
1	Introducing artificial intelligence (A.I.) and expert systems into university curricula increases students' creativity and performance.	4.26	0.71
2	Introducing A.I. and expert systems into the university curricula enhances students' ability to think creatively.	4.24	0.79
3	Introducing A.I. and expert systems into the curriculum helps students respond quickly and creatively to new situations and circumstances.	4.05	0.77
4	Introducing A.I. and expert systems into the curriculum develops students' perception and imagination.	3.48	0.97
5	Introducing A.I. and expert systems into the curriculum helps students to solve problems presented in the absence of complete information creatively.	3.61	1.11
6	Introducing A.I. and expert systems into university curricula increases students' ability to discover knowledge creatively.	3.82	1.06
7	A.I. and expert systems play a vital role in giving students the ability to manage difficult and complex situations.	3.49	1.13
8	A.I. and expert systems in university curricula increase students' pleasure during the lecture.	3.94	0.94
9	A.I. in university curricula increases students' ability to learn and understand based on past experiences.	3.87	0.92
10	Introducing A.I. and expert systems increase students' ability to develop creatively.	3.75	1.00
11	A.I. and expert systems in university curricula increase students' ability to understand and perceive visual matters.	3.86	0.90
12	A.I. and expert systems increase students' ability to innovate and renew creatively.	4.00	0.94
13	Introducing A.I. and expert systems in university curricula enhances students' creative skills.	3.80	1.03
14	A.I. and expert systems in university curricula creatively improve students' decision-making.	3.95	0.88
15	A.I. and expert systems in the curriculum teach students the skill of interpretation.	3.81	0.89
16	A.I. and expert systems help students develop their performance.	3.68	0.93
17	Introducing A.I. and expert systems in the university curriculum help students creatively apply knowledge.	3.67	0.78
18	A.I. and expert systems in the curriculum enable students to creatively present information.	3.78	0.86
19	A.I. and expert systems in the curriculum help students creatively carry out their	3.97	0.97

	assigned tasks.		
20	A.I. and expert systems in the curriculum help students understand the information quickly.	4.02	0.90
21	A.I. and expert systems help students obtain timely and accurate information.	4.14	0.90
22	Introducing A.I. and expert systems in university curricula enable students to keep abreast of technological developments.	3.96	1.03
23	A.I. and expert systems help students choose the best alternative.	4.12	0.78
24	Introducing A.I. and expert systems in university curricula increase student productivity.	4.12	0.95
25	Introducing A.I. and expert systems in university curricula enhances student intelligence.	3.89	0.90

Table 2: Summary of questionnaire results

Table 2 presents the means and standard deviations of the questionnaire responses. Regarding RQ1 ("How do faculty assess the effectiveness of introducing A.I. and expert systems in the curricula and teaching methods of university education colleges?"), the findings indicate above-neutral attitudes among faculty with means ranging between 3.48 and 4.26. The lowest scoring items related to A.I.'s ability to help develop students' perception and imagination (item 4), giving students the ability to manage difficult and complex situations (item 7), and creatively solve problems presented in the absence of complete information (item 5).

Regarding RQ2 ("Does the effectiveness of introducing A.I. and expert systems in the curricula and teaching methods of university education colleges vary according to variables such as gender, educational qualification, and experience?"), independent-sample t-tests and ANOVA were applied to measure differences between means depending on the gender, educational qualification, and experience. Table 3 presents the results of a t-test analyzing differences according to gender. Although female faculty considered A.I. to be more useful and practical than their male counterparts, there was no statistically significant difference between assessments based on gender.

<i>Gender</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P</i>
<i>Male</i>	55	3.870	0.554	-0.423	54	0.673
<i>Female</i>	38	3.921	0.601		37	

Table 3: Test Results for independent sample *t-test* to detect variances by gender variable

Table 4 summarizes the results of the t-test assessing differences in faculty perceptions according to academic qualifications. There was a statistically significant difference in faculty's understanding of A.I., whereby participants with master's degrees more commonly assessed the use of such technology as useful and practical ($t=2.457, p<0.05$).

The degree of freedom has calculated using the formula of $(n-1)$ where n is the sample size. Therefore, there are 39 degrees of freedom for MA and 52 degrees of freedom for a Ph.D.

Degree	N	Mean	SD	T	Df
MA	40	4.055	0.477	2.475	39
Ph.D.	53	3.767	0.609		52

Table 4. Differences in perception based on academic qualifications

As shown by Table 5, an ANOVA found no statistical difference between participants' perceptions of AI-based on teaching experience.

Variance Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	p
Within Groups	1.535	2	0.767	2.425	0.094
Between Groups	28.482	90	0.316		
Total	30.016	92	1.083		

Table 5: Results of an ANOVA measuring difference based on experience

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study used a questionnaire to assess UAE faculty members' attitudes towards the usefulness and effectiveness of A.I. in enhancing learning. Although overall, the participants reported that A.I. and Expert systems to be a useful tool in fostering students' innovation and creative thinking, the lowest scores were related to the role of A.I. and expert systems in developing students' perception and imagination (item 4), providing students with the ability to deal with complex cases (item 7). Faculty also had somewhat less confidence in the capacity of A.I. to assist problem-solving in the absence of complete information (item 5). Claudé and Combe (2018) described A.I. as a useful tool for managing complex situations; however, this study's finding indicates the limits of A.I. and the continued need for teachers to help guide students to address complex problems and obtain the necessary information to solve them. A study on the use of intelligent information systems in biomedical education highlighted the importance of students' use of search engines, bibliographic websites and library resources to support their research (Aparicio et al., 2018). Zawacki-Richter's (2019) meta-analysis demonstrated that faculty used A.I. tools to provide teaching content to students, it was generally combined with support by giving feedback and hints on to solve questions related to the content, as well as detecting students' difficulties/errors.

The lack of significant difference in faculty perceptions of A.I. according to gender aligns with previous findings regarding the impact of gender on attitudes toward technology (Imhof et al. 2007; North and Noyes, 2002; Teo et al. 2015, 2016

In the context of the Arab Gulf region, there is limited research on educators' attitudes toward A.I.; however, we can compare the results with findings on attitudes toward other educational technology tools. Al-Emran et al. 's (2016) study of attitudes toward mobile learning in Oman and UAE similarly found no statistical difference between male and female educators' perspectives, which they attributed to equal levels of use and experience. However, Alwraikat and Al Tokhaim's (2014) large-scale study of educators at King Saud University, found that female instructors' attitudes, towards mobile learning, were significantly more positive than that of male instructors. Al-Hunaiyyan et al. (2017), in the study of Instructors age and gender differences in the acceptance of mobile learning, found that the younger instructors were more likely to accept the mobile learning compare to the elderly instructors. Additionally, the study affirmed Alwraikat and Al Tokhaim's (2014) study findings that female instructors were more favorable to mobile learning compared to male counterparts.

The lack of difference based on experience suggests that the participants are using this technology with a high degree of mastery regardless of experience. Therefore, they view the same impact on students after the inclusion in the teaching methods and curriculum. Teachers' performance and interaction are at the same level, despite their experience. Other studies in the Arab Gulf region similarly identified no differences in attitudes toward mobile learning based on faculty members' expertise (Al-Emran et al., 2016; Eltahir et al., 2019). Gebhardt (2018), in the study on Adaptive Learning Courseware as a Tool to Build Foundational Content Mastery: Evidence from Principles of Microeconomics, also found that the use of the courseware promoted the student's mastery of concepts on the principles of Microeconomics.

Based on the findings, the researchers offer two main recommendations:

- 1) A.I. and expert systems introduced into the curricula and teaching methods of university education college. The two have a significant impact on students' creativity and excellence return.
- 2) Further research, similar to this study, must be conducted on applications of A.I. in higher education systems in developing countries, and different perspectives should have explored. The reason for choosing this study is most of the developing countries are yet to embrace e-learning due to some limiting factors such as cultures, economy, and the level of technological development. For example, this study focused on teachers' perceptions of learning-facing tools, i.e., software that responds to students' needs and is used to receive and understand new information (Baker & Smith, 2019). Future

research should examine precisely how faculty members use A.I. to support students' learning and the level of acceptance of A.I. in educational colleges in developing countries.

This study has several limitations. First, the sample was limited to the college of education faculty rather than encompassing faculty across departments. Future studies can examine perceptions of A.I. educational technology across disciplines to evaluate if any differences can be related to educators' area of expertise. Future research can also incorporate additional variables such as age to measure teachers' perceptions, as well as measures of teacher self-efficacy and mastery of A.I. and expert systems.

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Author Information

Hani Yousef Jarrah

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0243-0106>

Al-ain university

Suad Alwaely

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3980-7904>

United Arab Emirates

College Of Education And Social Science

United Arab Emirates- Abu Dhabi
